

SOCIOECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

Livelihood

Profitability of urea supergranules in rice

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We compared the economics of N applied as urea supergranule (USG) and as prilled urea (PU) at three N levels in field experiments 1985 and 1986 wet seasons, in a randomized block design with four replications. Experimental soil was silt loam, classified as Aquic Hapludoll. The site lies about 30 km south of the Shivalik range of the Himalayas, 29° N, 79°29' E,

Comparative economics of USC placement and PU split application.^a Uttar Pradesh, India, 1985 and 1986.

Item	N rate (kg/ha)		
	29	58	87
Labor d/ha for USG placement	8	10	10
Wages (\$/d)	1.21	1.21	1.21
Total labor cost/ha for USG placement (\$)	9.68	12.10	12.10
Incremental yield (t/ha) from USG	0.40	0.80	1.00
Added value of rice ^b (\$)	44.80	89.60	112.00
Labor d/ha for basal application of PU	2	2	2
Labor d/ha for top-dressing of PU	1	1	1
Total labor d/ha for PU application	3	3	3
Total labor cost for PU (\$)	3.63	3.63	3.63
Difference in labor cost (USG-PU) (\$)	6.05	8.47	8.47
Difference in material cost (USG-PU) (\$)	1.08	2.15	3.22
Total additional cost (\$)	7.13	10.62	11.69
Additional return from USG (\$)	37.67	78.98	100.31

^aMean of 1985 and 1986. ^bPrice of rough rice = \$112.00/t.

and is a subtropical, subhumid climatic zone.

Rice cultivar Pant Dhan 4 was transplanted (45-d-old seedlings) at 20 × 20-cm spacing 15 Jul both years. PKZn (18 kg P, 33 kg K, 10 kg Zn/ha) was broadcast and incorporated 1 d before transplanting (DBT). USG was placed 8-10 cm deep 1 d after transplanting in the middle of every four hills. PU was applied 1/2 broadcast and incorporated 1 DBT, 1/4 topdressed at tillering, and 1/4

topdressed 5-7 d before panicle initiation. All costs were the same except for N.

Prices were \$112/t for rough rice, \$0.37/kg N for PU, and \$0.41/kg N for USG. Cost of N application was estimated as \$1.21/labor d, with 3 labor d/ha for PU and 8-10 labor d/ha for USG.

Increased yield with USG compensated for additional costs of application (see table). □

EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

Training and technology transfer research

Information gaps in transmitting rice recommendations to farmers

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Technological innovations in rice culture are usually transmitted to farming communities through extension recommendations. A recommendation will contain a certain amount of information that farmers can use to improve their productivity.

In many instances, however, we find an information gap. Information gap refers to the amount of information contained in the information input, but not in the information output.

The Training and Visit (T & V) System of Agricultural Extension is an extension management tool. Special

attention has been given to its implementation in the rice subsector of Sri Lanka. The T & V System is organized to disseminate information from research stations through extension to farmers, and vice versa.

We focused on selected rice recommendations given by the T & V System. This study reports the intensity of information gaps. Data were collected in one wet zone district of southern Sri Lanka during the major rice-growing season, Sep 1986-Feb 1987.

Subject Matter Officers (SMOs) and Agricultural Officers (AOs) of the district were interviewed. Their extension recommendations were considered as information input. Information items were extracted from selected recommendations and standard scores computed. A sample of 100 farmers were surveyed to obtain the information output.